

International Journal of peer to peer networks(IJP2P)

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SCOPE OF THE JOURNAL

The International Journal of peer-to-peer networking is a quarterly open access peer-reviewed journal that publishes articles that contribute new results in all areas of P2P Networks. The journal provides a platform to disseminate new ideas and new research, advance theories, and propagate best practices in the area of P2P networking. This will include works that relate to peer-to-peer systems, peer-to-peer applications, grid systems, large-scale distributed systems, and overlay networks. The journal offers a forum in which academics, consultants, and practitioners in a variety of fields can exchange ideas to further research and improve practices in all areas of P2P.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the journal by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of P2P networks.

Topics of interest within the scope of this issue include, but are not limited to, the following areas:

- Advances in theoretical foundations of P2P
- Commercial applications
- Cooperation and collaboration in P2P systems
- Delay-tolerant P2P systems
- Higher-level query support in P2P systems
- Mobile P2P
- Overlay architectures and topologies
- Overlay monitoring and management
- P2P and wireless convergence
- P2P applications and services
- P2P economics
- P2P grids
- P2P information retrieval
- P2P overlay interaction with underlying infrastructure
- P2P systems over mobile networks
- P2P technology and sensors
- P2P workload characterization and simulation
- Performance and robustness of P2P systems
- Protocols and Algorithms for Mobile and Wireless Peer-to-peer Networks
- Security in P2P systems
- Self-organization in P2P systems
- Semantic overlay networks and semantic query routing in P2P systems
- Social networks
- Trust, Reputation and Fairness in P2P Systems
- ad hoc and sensor networks

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Submissions are accepted for review with the understanding that the same work has been neither submitted to, nor published in, another publication. Simultaneous submission to other publications will result in immediate rejection of the paper. Papers are not within the journal scope will be rejected immediately after the pre review process.

All manuscripts will be subject to a well-established, fair, unbiased peer review and refereeing procedure, and are considered on the basis of their significance, novelty and usefulness to the Journals readership. The reviewing structure will always ensure the anonymity of the referees & it will be reviewed by 3 experts in the field. The review output will be one of the following decisions:

1. Accept
2. Accept with minor changes
3. Weak Accept with major changes
4. Reject

The review process may take approximately two ~three months to be completed. The Editor reserves the right to reject a paper if it does not meet the aims and scope of the journal, it is not revised well.

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